

In these optically active phenylurea derivatives, the maximum rotation was found in the case of *N-m*-nitrophenyl-*N'*-3-methylcaproylurea, $[\alpha]_D^{20} +110.5$ ($l=1$) and the minimum in the case of *N-m*-tolyl-*N'*-3-methylcaproylurea, $[\alpha]_D^{20} +25.5$ ($l=1$).

Infrared spectra: All the compounds, in general gave the following bands: 1500-1480 (NH stretch), 1690-1570 (C=O stretch), -CO.NH.CO- stretching vibration 1640-1740 (CO.NH.CO stretch) and 710-690 cm^{-1} (CH stretch).

Antibacterial activity: The purified product was screened for antibacterial activity by cup-plate method using a species of gram-positive bacteria, *i.e.* *S. aureus* and a species of gram-negative bacteria, *i.e.* *E. coli*. Testing was carried out in ethanol solution at the concentration of 10 mg ml^{-1} .

The zone of inhibition of the test solutions were recorded.

The zone of inhibition against *S. aureus* was found maximum in the case of *N-o*-tolyl-*N'*-3-methylcaproylurea (8 m.m.) and minimum for *N-p*-tolyl-*N'*-3-methylcaproylurea (3 m.m.).

Similarly, for *E. coli* the maximum zone was found for *N-m*-chlorophenyl-*N'*-3-methylcaproylurea (5 m.m.) and minimum value occurred in the case of *N-p*-nitrophenyl-*N'*-3-methylcaproylurea (2 m.m.).

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Studies on Chalcones: Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-Aryl-4-carboxy-6-acetylquinoline and 2-Aryl-4-carboxy-6-benzalacetquinolines

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QUINOLINE derivatives possess wide therapeutic activity, *viz.* antiseptic¹, analgesics², tryphocidal³, germicidal⁴, antitubercular⁵, anthelmintics⁶ and antiserotonin⁷. Chalcones also possess anthelmintic⁸,

antimitotic and antimicrobial activity¹⁰. With a view to prepare better therapeutically active compounds, we have synthesised 2-aryl-4-carboxy-6-acetylquinoline of type (I)¹¹ and condensed them with benzaldehyde to get chalcones (II). The constitutions of acetoquinoline and chalcone were supported by ir spectra. The ir spectra (KBr) of 2-phenyl-4-carboxy-6-acetylquinoline and 2-phenyl-4-carboxy-6-benzalacetquinolines showed bands at 1490 (C=N) and 1590 (C=C), 1360 (CH₃-CO) 1440 (COOH), and 1480 (C=N), 1590 (C=C), 1310 (CH=CH), 1670 (C=O) and 1440 cm^{-1} (COOH), respectively¹². The products were screened for antibacterial activity.

where R = Aryl

Experimental

2-Aryl-4-carboxy-6-acetylquinoline: A mixture of purified benzaldehyde (0.01 mol), freshly distilled pyruvic acid (0.01 mol) and absolute ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed and a solution of *p*-aminoacetophenone (0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol (25 ml) was added slowly with frequent shaking. The mixture was further refluxed for 3 h and allowed to stand overnight. The product was filtered and crystallised from ethanol. The physical constants are recorded in Table 1.

2-Aryl-4-carboxy-6-benzalacetquinolines: Benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in ethanol (95%, 10 ml) was added to the mixture of 2-aryl-4-carboxy-6-acetylquinoline (0.01 mol) in ethanol (95%, 25 ml), aqueous sodium hydroxide (1%, 6 ml) and rectified spirit (95%, 10 ml) and stirred at 20-30° for 2-3 h. Content were then kept for 24 h at 0-10°, filtered and the product was isolated by acidification and crystallised from ethanol. The physical constants are recorded in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

Antimicrobial activity: The purified products were screened for antibacterial activity by cup-plate method¹³ using a species of gram-positive bacteria, *i.e.* *Staphylococcus aureus* and a species of gram-negative bacteria, *i.e.* *Escherichia coli*. The testing was carried out in ethanol at a concentration of

NOTES

TABLE I—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS OF 2-ARYL-4-CARBOXY-6-ACETYLQUINOLINE (I)

Sl. no.	R	Molecular formula	M.p. °C	Yield	N% Found (Calcd.)	Diameter of zone of inhibition in mm (0.5 mg test solution)	
						<i>S. aureus</i> 24 h	<i>E. coli</i> 24 h
1	Phenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ NO ₄ *	173-75	92	4.75 (4.81)	10	—
2	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ NO ₄	125-27	82	4.40 (4.36)	40	—
3	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ NO ₄	192-94	83	4.56 (4.56)	40	15
4	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ NO ₄	164-66	86	4.40 (4.56)	44	—
5	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ NO ₄	157-59	81	4.40 (4.56)	40	—
6	3-Bromo-2-hydroxy-phenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ BrNO ₄	190-92	78	3.35 (3.63)	40	—
7	3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxy-phenyl	C ₁₆ H ₉ Br ₂ NO ₄	175-77	89	3.10 (3.01)	44	—
8	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₆	155-57	71	3.40 (3.33)	40	—
9	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ ClNO ₄	138-40	73	4.20 (4.30)	—	25
10	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ ClNO ₄	188-90	78	4.10 (4.30)	—	—

* Correct C, H analyses.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS OF CHALCONES (II)

Sl. no.	R	Molecular formula	M.p. °C	Yield	N% Found (Calcd.)	Diameter of zone of inhibition in mm (0.5 mg test solution)	
						<i>S. aureus</i> 24 h	<i>E. coli</i> 24 h
1	Phenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ NO ₄ *	158-60	64	3.60 (3.69)	15	—
2	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ NO ₄	95	56	3.40 (3.42)	22	10
3	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ NO ₄	110	54	3.51 (3.54)	12	15
4	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ NO ₄	195-97	60	3.50 (3.54)	28	10
5	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ NO ₄	147-48	61	3.48 (3.54)	20	—
6	3-Bromo-2-hydroxy-phenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ BrNO ₄	132-34	57	2.87 (2.95)	—	—
7	3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ Br ₂ NO ₄	105	53	2.43 (2.53)	—	—
8	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₆	300	54	6.40 (6.60)	15	—
9	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ ClNO ₄	153-55	50	3.25 (3.38)	40	—
10	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ ClNO ₄	198-200	51	3.22 (3.38)	40	—

* Correct C, H analyses.

10 mg ml⁻¹. *o*-Chlorophenyl and *p*-chlorophenyl derivatives of type (I) are highly active against *S. aureus* while *p*-anisyl, *o*-hydroxyphenyl and *m*-hydroxyphenyl are highly active against *E. coli*. *m*-Hydroxyphenyl, 3,5-dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl of type II are highly active against *S. aureus*, while *o*-hydroxyphenyl and *p*-chlorophenyl derivatives are active against *E. coli*. This antimicrobial activity is less as compared to well known antibiotics like chloromycetin, penicillin, sulphadruugs, etc.

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Synthesis of 3,5-Dimethyl-4-(substituted-sulfonamidobenzene azo, 4-sulfophenyl and 4-sulfonaphthyl azo)-1(H)-(hetero substituted) pyrazoles and Evaluation of Their Antibacterial Properties

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Great importance is being given to pyrazole derivatives due to their uses in therapeutics. Pyrazole compounds with 3- and 5-methyl group are found to possess hypoglycemic activity¹. Isoxazole sulfa-drugs are stable substances and they are characterised by low toxicity and strong activity *in vivo* against bacteria². Substituted-3(2H)pyridazinones are shown to possess antibacterial and anti-fungal activities³.

In continuation of our work in pyrazole series⁴, we wish to report the synthesis of few more compounds, viz. 3,5-dimethyl-4-(substituted sulfonamidobenzene azo, 4-sulfophenyl and 4-sulfonaphthyl azo)-1(H)-(hetero substituted)pyrazole compounds, and screening of their antibacterial properties.

Substituted sulfonamidobenzene azo, benzene azo-4-sulfonic acid and naphthalene azo-4-sulfonic acid derivatives of 2,4-diketopentane (acetylacetone) were prepared by coupling the 2,4-diketopentane with diazotised sulfonamido base, sulfanilic acid and naphthionic acid, respectively (Ia, Ib) in the presence of sodium acetate⁵. The azo derivatives of 2,4-diketopentane obtained was then reacted with four substituted carboxy hydrazides, viz. (i) 3,5-dimethyl-1(H)-(4-benzoyl hydrazide)pyrazole, (ii) 3,5-dimethyl-1(H)-(4-nitrophenyl)-4-(methyl carbonyl hydrazide)pyrazole, (iii) 5-phenyl-3-(2-oxymethylene

carbonyl hydrazide)phenyl isoxazole, and (iv) 6-methoxy-2-(4-benzoyl hydrazide)-3(2H)pyridazinone, to furnish the corresponding *N*-substituted-3,5-dimethyl-4-(substituted sulfonamidobenzene azo)pyrazoles of the type IIa and *N*-substituted-3,5-dimethyl-4-(4-sulfophenyl azo and 4-sulfonaphthyl azo)pyrazoles of the type IIb. Hydrazones of the above carboxyhydrazides were also obtained by treating with the azo derivatives of 2,4-diketopentane.

Experimental

The sulfonamides were prepared by standard methods^{6,7}. The azo compounds from 2,4-diketopentane were obtained in 48-75% yield by the method reported earlier⁵. The melting points were taken in open capillary and are uncorrected. The elemental analysis of all compounds (C, H, N and S) was found to be satisfactory.

3,5-Dimethyl-4-(substituted sulfonamidobenzene azo)pyrazoles: Equimolar quantities of the appropriate carbonyl hydrazide was reacted with 2,4-diketo-3-substituted azo pentane in ethanol under reflux to give the corresponding hydrazones, which were crystallised from aqueous ethanol, and yields ranging from 70-85% (Table 1).

TABLE 1—HYDRAZONES FROM 2,4-DIKETO-3-(SUBSTITUTED SULFONAMIDOBENZENE AZO, 4-SULFOPHENYL AZO AND 4-SULFONAPHTHYL AZO)PENTANE

Sl. no.	X	R	M.p. °C
1	HOOCCH ₂ -	R _a	192
2	H ₅ C ₂ -	R _a	214
3	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	R _a	217
4	HOOCCH ₂ -	R _b	178
5	H ₅ C ₂ -	R _b	106
6	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	R _b	218
7	HOOCCH ₂ -	R _c	292
8	H ₅ C ₂ -	R _c	126
9	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	R _c	208
10	H ₅ C ₂ -	R _d	254
11	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	R _d	204
12	4-SO ₂ H-C ₆ H ₄ -	R _a	278
13	4-SO ₂ H-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	R _a	310
14	4-SO ₂ H-C ₆ H ₄ -	R _b	104
15	4-SO ₂ H-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	R _b	299
16	4-SO ₂ H-C ₆ H ₄ -	R _c	152
17	4-SO ₂ H-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	R _c	330
18	4-SO ₂ H-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	R _d	247

The above hydrazones were converted to the corresponding pyrazoles by refluxing it in glacial acetic acid. The same pyrazoles were also obtained by refluxing 2,4-diketo-3-substituted azo pentane with the respective carbonyl hydrazide in glacial acetic acid for 8-10 h. The separated products were filtered and crystallised from ethanol with yields ranging from 45-75% (Table 2).

3,5-Dimethyl-4-(4-sulfophenyl azo and 4-sulfonaphthyl azo)pyrazoles: 2,4-Diketo-3-(4-sulfophenyl azo) pentane and 2,4-diketo-3-(4-sulfonaphthyl azo) pentane were prepared using the reported proce-